

SIMCor

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Executive summary

This document was developed to provide a *standard operating procedure* (SOP) on the generation of virtual cohorts and their validation for use in in-silico trials. It aims to establish a systematic approach to building and validating virtual cohorts, for immediate use in device-effect simulation and thereby facilitate the in-silico trials. Considering the wide possibilities of ‘context(s) of use’ for virtual cohorts, we present a broad set of recommendations, building on the advances and the specific learnings from the two SIMCor use cases: *transcatheter aortic valve implantation* (TAVI) and *pulmonary artery pressure sensors* (PAPS). The SOP presents the cycle of development, validation, and application of virtual cohorts of pigs and humans, as applied to the above-mentioned use cases. Moreover, in the *Outlook* section, we sketch the broad perspectives on critical factors that need to be considered while attempting to generate virtual cohorts. Also, highlighted are the nuances related to their validation for different ‘context(s) of use’. This deliverable also includes two tangible applications of virtual cohorts, on the aortic valve and the pulmonary artery, for predicting patient-specific treatment outcomes like leakage post-implantation or device migration.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AA	Ascending aorta
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
AVA	Aortic valve area
CFD	Computational fluid mechanics
CHA	Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin
CM&S	Computational modelling & simulation
CSV	Comma separated value
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HF	Heart failure
ISCT	In-silico clinical trials
LPA	Left pulmonary artery
LVOT	Left ventricular outflow tract
LYN	Lynkeus
MEE	Model execution environment
MPA	Main pulmonary artery
PA	Pulmonary artery
PAPS	Pulmonary artery pressure sensor
PVL	Paravalvular leakage
R&D	Research and development
RPA	Right pulmonary artery
SOP	Standard operating procedure
STJ	Sino-tubular junction
TAVI	Transcatheter aortic valve implantation
TRE	Trusted research environment
TUE	Technical University Eindhoven
UCL	University College London
UTBV	Transilvania University of Braşov
V&V	Validation and verification
VC	Virtual cohort
VCG	Virtual Cohort Generator
VPHi	Virtual Physiological Human Institute
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Cover page of the SOP D4.3

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Purpose and field of application:

Generating and validating cohorts of virtual patients and animals, for use in numerical predictive models in the context of medical device design, development, testing and validation. These virtual cohorts, composed of reconstructed geometries and synthetic data mimicking the properties of real data sets, provide an invaluable resource for investigating various safety and efficacy aspects of medical devices through in-silico clinical trials.

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Introduction

In the field of cardiovascular medicine, the ability to analyse vast amounts of patient data is vital for developing effective treatment strategies. With the advent of advanced computational techniques, the creation of virtual cohorts has emerged as a powerful tool for studying patient populations and conducting clinical research. These virtual cohorts, composed of de-identified patient data, reconstructed geometries and synthetic data, provide an invaluable resource for investigating various safety and efficacy aspects of cardiovascular medical devices.

Virtual cohorts have been proposed to enable researchers to overcome many limitations associated with real cohort studies, such as time, cost, privacy preservation, limited population representativity, special populations and logistical constraints. Moreover, virtual cohorts offer the potential for exploring rare or complex conditions that may be difficult to capture in a limited sample size. By harnessing the power of these virtual cohorts, SIMCor aims at expanding our understanding of cardiovascular diseases, refine treatment strategies, improve patient outcomes, and accelerating the translation of innovation to patients by means of realistic in-silico clinical trials.

Purpose

This *standard operating procedure* (SOP) aims to establish a systematic approach to building and validating virtual cohorts in cardiovascular medicine and beyond. It also provides guidance for using virtual cohorts for device-effect simulation, which in turn facilitates the in-silico trials in the *Virtual Research Environment* (VRE) created in SIMCor. By adhering to this procedure, researchers and clinicians can ensure consistency, accuracy, and reliability of the cohort data, fostering robust and reproducible research outcomes. This SOP is part of a comprehensive ensemble of guidelines and SOPs, encompassing data acquisition, preprocessing, validation procedures, and reporting, enabling the creation of reliable virtual cohorts that reflect real-world patient populations.

This SOP has been developed in collaboration with leading experts in cardiovascular in-silico medicine as part of the SIMCor consortium. It aligns as much as possible with current state of the art, best practices and regulatory requirements for building virtual cohorts, handling patient data, ensuring compliance with ethical guidelines and privacy regulations, such as the European *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR)¹.

This document is composed of 3 parts:

1. *Part A: Guidance for the development and validation of a virtual cohort.* It will be partly illustrated by an example of the *Virtual Cohort Generator* (VCG), developed in SIMCor by TUE, that primarily creates synthetic geometries of stenosed aortic valve. Additionally, specific exemplary applications of the general procedure for cohort generation and validation, as well as their relevance in the context of device implantation and in-silico trials is provided using the two use-cases investigated in SIMCor:
 - *Transcatheter aortic valve implantation* (TAVI): minimally invasive implantation of a biological valve prosthesis into the aortic root via catheterization.
 - *Pulmonary arterial pressure sensor* (PAPS): implantation of a pressure sensor into the left or right pulmonary artery aiming to measure the instantaneous blood pressure within the pulmonary artery of patients suffering from heart failure.

These specific examples will be briefly summarised (at high-level) in the main text of the document as follows:

Exemplary use case - specific processing step

This format is used to present practical applications of the general recommendations provided in this manuscript.

Further to the general guidance on the virtual cohort generation and validation, the specific application of using the virtual cohorts within the TAVI and PAPS use cases are detailed in the following sections:

2. *Part B: Application of the TAVI VCG (TUE) and in-silico trial in the SIMCor VRE.*
3. *Part C: Application of the PAPS VCG (CHA) in the SIMCor VRE.*

The methodological details and validation results are not part of this document, rather covered in the respective SIMCor deliverables. For the reader's interest, these are duly cross-referenced in the SOP, wherever applicable.

¹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

Scope

This SOP was developed by the SIMCor consortium experts, and as such it reflects the know-how of the consortium on building and validating virtual cohorts for cardiac medical device development and provide guidance on how to use virtual cohorts for in-silico trials within the SIMCor VRE². It is aimed at modellers from the field but may also be applicable beyond cardiovascular applications. By following this SOP, stakeholders can maximise the quality and reliability of cohort data, foster collaboration among different institutions, enhance robustness and credibility of *computational modeling & simulation* (CM&S) results and accelerate scientific discoveries that have the potential to transform patient care. More practically, this SOP should guide the development of virtual cohorts using multiple approaches for virtual cohort generation, as well as help with the validation strategy of such cohorts according to existing standards. It is also aimed at guiding users through the SIMCor VRE to leverage the VCG developed by TUE in SIMCor.

² <https://simcor.unitbv.ro/>

Definitions

Virtual patient: A virtual patient is a member of a virtual cohort that mimics the physiology of a real patient as accurately as possible *prior to* and *after* medical intervention. A virtual patient consists of a geometrical domain of interest, a physiology-based model, complemented with realistic boundary conditions and/or model parameter values (e.g., mechanical wall properties).

Synthetic data: artificial data either produced by interpolation of real patient data, and/or by generative models. Synthetic data should maintain the same statistical properties of the real cohorts while preserving their privacy.

Virtual cohort: a “set of virtual patients that mimics a cohort of real patients with respect to all reasonably expected patient states, patient dynamics and evolution of patient condition which might occur in practice”³. Each virtual patient of the cohort is an anatomical and physiological model, characterised by its own parameter set, that can predict the same endpoint that would be observed in clinical practice. Moreover, the variation between virtual patients represents the real population’s variability⁴. In SIMCor, we have chosen to also refer to a virtual cohort if it consists of multiple synthetic geometries. The reason for this is that in most cases proper geometric parameterisation can be considered as one integrated part of developing a virtual patient, independent of the model that will be applied, while the physiology-based model in the end depends on the context of use.

In-silico trials: An in-silico trial refers to the use of individualised computer simulations in a cohort of virtual patients during the development or regulatory evaluation of a medicinal product, medical device, or medical intervention.

Virtual Research Environment: the cloud-based platform that provides researchers and/or clinicians with access to preclinical, clinical and synthetic data, as well as access to a virtual cohort generator (e.g., for geometries of aorta), simulation models (e.g., to study device effects), and other computational tools (e.g., R-Statistical Environment), acquired and developed in the course of SIMCor.

³ J. G. Chase, J. C. Preiser, J. L. Dickson, A. Pironet, Y. S. Chiew, C. G. Pretty, G. M. Shaw, B. Benyo, K. Moeller, S. Safaei, M. Tawhai, P. Hunter, T. Desai, Next-generation, personalised, model-based critical care medicine: A state-of-the art review of in silico virtual patient models, methods, and cohorts, and how to validate them. *Biomed. Eng. Online*. **17** (2018), pp. 1–29

⁴ M. Viceconti, C. Cobelli, T. Haddad, A. Himes, B. Kovatchev, M. Palmer, In silico assessment of biomedical products: The conundrum of rare but not so rare events in two case studies. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part H J. Eng. Med.* **231**, 455–466 (2017).

Part A: guidance for the development and validation of the virtual cohorts

Overview

A **virtual patient** can be described as a numerical model that provides realistic physiological responses. These models can have a limited geometrical domain of interest, complemented with realistic boundary conditions and/or model parameter values (e.g., mechanical wall properties). When the input parameters (e.g., geometry, physiological parameters, demography) of such a numerical model is varied, multiple candidate virtual patients can be realised. However, some combinations of inputs might be physiologically unrealistic because the exact high-dimensional input space is difficult to define, especially for all possible dependencies/correlations between inputs. To remove these unrealistic candidates, acceptance criteria are defined and used to filter out these unrealistic samples (see Figure 1). Moreover, these filters allow for selecting only those patients that have specific characteristics, e.g., only moderate stenosis severities. In the end, a virtual patient is thus a numerical model and a parameterisation that produces physiologically realistic simulations. Collectively, the numerical model and the filters that generate these populations of virtual patients are referred to as a VCG.

Ensuring that the virtual patients generated by VCGs are realistic, a series of **virtual cohort validation** steps are necessary. Broadly, these include model **verification and validation**, **input sampling and output filtering** strategies, as well as **cross-validation**.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the methodology for virtual cohort generation. Sampling input space for a possible candidate for inclusion into the virtual cohort and filtering out samples that are physiologically plausible (green).

Generation and validation of virtual cohorts

The following section briefly describes the different steps related to how virtual cohorts are generated and validated. For an extensive reading on the model development, verification and validation for the VCG and virtual cohorts, the relevant SIMCor deliverables are referenced.

Phase 1: model development

The generation of virtual cohorts begins with the creation of a realistic physiology-based model of the domain of interest (i.e., solid mechanics, haemodynamics, device-structure/fluid interactions, or combinations of them).

Development and validation of physiology-based models require real-world clinical data that include geometrical information (e.g., 3D geometries, segmented medical images of patients), functional data (e.g., blood pressure, flow, velocities and/or wall movements throughout the domain and at the boundaries of the domain of interest). This implies a collection and curation of diverse sets of input data from multiple different modalities. Guidelines regarding the acquisition and pre-processing of clinical and preclinical data for the creation of virtual cohorts were detailed in previous SOPs as follows:

- *D4.1 - SOP for data acquisition for in-silico models (UCL, M18)* details the procedure for clinical (secondary use) and preclinical in-vivo data acquisition for virtual cohorts.
 - The procedure for the definition of the required data, their acquisition and storage processes, including legal and data privacy considerations for clinical data are outlined.
 - The guidelines for the acquisition of preclinical animal data following best and lawful practice, with due considerations to rationale of animal experiments and factoring animal welfare, are presented.
- *D4.2 - SOP for data processing for in-silico models (CHA, M12)* presents the procedures and workflows for the processing of clinical data (in particular, imaging data) in the view of generating virtual cohorts.
 - Standards and guidelines for data quality, data formats and data exchange are summarised.

Note that the above SOPs also include recommendations to collect and share data across national boundaries and multiple clinical centres, while complying with regulations and guidelines regarding data privacy, anonymisation, good clinical practice, and *findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability* (FAIR) principles or refer to other guidance documents relevant for these issues. Data sharing across international centres is most likely not avoidable as the physiology-based models, when serving as the core of a virtual cohort generation, should in the end be representative, and validated, for the complete population, which can often not be assessed from individual centres alone.

The numerical model of the generator needs to be verified (*does it produce results that it should produce given the governing equations/algorithms?*) and validated (*does it produce realistic results that mimic the physiology/dynamics of the system?*)⁵. Moreover, the accuracy of the calculations needs to be assessed.

⁵ V&V 40, A. S. M. E. (2018). Assessing credibility of computational modeling through verification and validation: application to medical devices. *The American Society of Mechanical Engineers*.

Development & validation of the VCG in SIMCor

In SIMCor, multiple computational models were developed to generate virtual cohorts of physiology (i.e., means of pressure drop) and geometries. Moreover, the individual steps of the VCG development and validation are fully described in the following public deliverables:

- *D7.1 - Definition of model output (TUE, M6)⁶*
- *D7.2 - First version of the simulation models (TUE, M9)⁷*
- *D7.3 - First version of definition of the input space (TUE, M12)⁸*
- *D7.4 - Sensitivity and uncertainty quantification toolbox (TUE, M15)⁹*
- *D7.5 - Uncertainty quantification and re-definition of input space (TUE, M18)¹⁰*
- *D7.8 - Validated virtual cohorts for in-silico trials (TUE, M36)¹¹.*

In the context of in-silico models, there are also guidelines on the SOPs for documentation (*D4.4 - Guidelines for documentation (IIB, M12)¹²*), analysis (*D4.5 - SOPs for in-silico analysis of TAVI (IIB, M24)¹³*) and validation (*D4.6 - SOPs for validation of in-silico models (BIO, M36)¹⁴*).

As soon as satisfying results have been obtained for a realistic subset of real patients (i.e., validated and with uncertainties quantified as acceptable within the context of use), the model can be used to generate virtual patients by varying the inputs and applying a filtering strategy to remove unrealistic input combinations. For the validation, the tiered strategy proposed by Chase et al.¹⁵ is adopted. This strategy consists of the 3 steps: (1) patient-specific validation, (2) self-validation and (3) cross validation, which are described in the following section.

VCGs in SIMCor

In SIMCo, multiple computational models that generate virtual cohorts were developed:

- **TAVI Prototype demonstrator:** Here, virtual patients are defined by an aortic valve geometry parameterised by statistical shape modes and a scaling factor, complemented by a peak systolic inflow and a *computational fluid mechanics* (CFD) surrogate model that calculates pressure differences across the valve. As a filtering strategy, the pressure difference is used. This generator has not been completely validated and only preliminary patient-level validations are performed.
- **TAVI geometry generator:** This generator creates synthetic aortic valve geometries and uses a filtering strategy that considers geometrical features (converging and diverging *left ventricular outflow tract* (LVOT), or the angle between LVOT and ascending aorta). For this generator, the patient-level and self-validation has been completed, while preliminary cross-validation results are also available (see D7.8).

⁶ Huberts, W. (2021). SIMCor. Deliverable 7.1: Definition of model output (TUE, M6). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6074808>.

⁷ Huberts, W. (2021). SIMCor. Deliverable 7.2: Definition of model templates (TUE, M9). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6146529>.

⁸ Huberts, W. (2021). SIMCor. Deliverable 7.3: First version of the definition of the input space (TUE, M12). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6150327>.

⁹ Huberts, W. (2022). SIMCor. Deliverable 7.4 - Sensitivity and uncertainty quantification toolbox (TUE, M15). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7036217>.

¹⁰ Huberts, W., Stiehm, M., Borowsky, F., & Oldeburg, J. (2022). SIMCor. Deliverable 7.5 - Uncertainty quantification and re-definition of input space (TUE, M18). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7041286>.

¹¹ To be made publicly available in Zenodo by June 2024.

¹² Stiehm, M., Brüning, J., Lesage, R., Cypionka, T., Oldenburg, J., Huberts, W., Rolf-Pissarczyk, M., Luther, Torsten, Staumont, B., & Geris, L. (2021). SIMCor. Deliverable 4.4: Guidelines for documentation (IIB, M12). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6150905>.

¹³ To be made publicly available in Zenodo by June 2024.

¹⁴ To be made publicly available in Zenodo by June 2024.

¹⁵ J. G. Chase, J. C. Preiser, J. L. Dickson, A. Pironet, Y. S. Chiew, C. G. Pretty, G. M. Shaw, B. Benyo, K. Moeller, S. Safaei, M. Tawhai, P. Hunter, T. Desai, Next-generation, personalised, model-based critical care medicine: A state-of-the art review of in silico virtual patient models, methods, and cohorts, and how to validation them. *Biomed. Eng. Online.* 17 (2018), pp. 1–29.

- **PAPS geometry generator:** This generator uses a large-scale virtual cohort of human and porcine pulmonary artery geometries and boundary conditions. From this large-scale cohort, sub-cohorts can be created using filtering strategies based on different geometric and demographic parameters. The underlying large-scale cohort is available (see D7.8). The selection procedure will be implemented into the SIMCor VRE. For this cohort, the patient-specific and self-validation steps have been successfully finalised.

Phase 2: validation

Step 1: patient-level validation

The first step of virtual cohort validation begins with the validation of the computational model. When the numerical model of the virtual cohort generator is successfully validated for the given context of use, it is deemed ready to produce a realistic subset of virtual patients. Thus, satisfying patient-level validation, whereby the model can realistically mimic the anatomy and physiology of real patients.

Step 2: self validation

The second step of validation of cohorts starts by defining the input space that captures the variation in the model parameters, which is present in the population and is based on *a priori* knowledge and literature data. Subsequently, the input space is sampled by using space-filling sampling strategies and the model is evaluated for each input sample. Thereafter, the model outcome is either accepted or rejected based on user-defined acceptance criteria. These criteria (or filters) are recommended for:

1. Removing non-realistic combinations of parameters that results from incomplete/sparse knowledge of the real population distributions of the inputs.
2. Filtering out specific cases prioritised by the stakeholders (e.g., clinicians).

It is important to recognise that the required model evaluations above are advised to be performed while using surrogate models, that are by definition fast-to-evaluate representations of the real model. This will in most cases significantly enhance the efficiency of the above-mentioned approach.

Another important issue is that a precise definition of the input space is often difficult to obtain and remains sparse, especially when multiple inputs are involved, with multiple interactions, and possible statistical dependencies/correlations. The use of a physiology-based model introduces known causalities between parameters, while the filter removes non-realistic input parameter combinations. In fact, after filtering the input sets, only the realistic realisations remain, which “redefines” the (sparse) input space.

To validate the generated virtual patients, the multidimensional population distributions of the virtual cohorts need to be compared to real distributions on specific user-defined features, e.g., the aortic valve opening areas. For this, the most accurate and proper statistical test needs to be selected. The completion of this phase of the cycle forms the self-validation step of the virtual patient cohort. If this step is unsatisfactory, the filter settings and model will iteratively be updated until the virtual patient cohort is accurately representing the real patients.

Step 3: cross-validation

The final validation phase of the virtual cohort generator consists of cross-validation. In this phase the patients that are generated by the virtual cohort generator are compared with an independent, but clinically matched, real patient cohort. The evaluation will be done on user-defined features and by using properly selected statistical tests that allow for multidimensional comparisons. Important is that in this step of the phase 2, the model, input space and filter settings are set and will not be adapted anymore.

Phase 3: virtual cohort generation

Following the above procedure for generating and validating virtual cohorts, it is expected to be possible to generate hundreds of anatomically plausible synthetic geometries and other data elements required for model personalisation. Further, filtering procedures should be implemented to select geometries and properties with certain morphologic or demographic parameters, such as specific shape properties, specific size ranges, or geometries representing a specific age group or those relevant for a medical intervention (clinically driven). Below, you can find a summary of different virtual cohorts generated within SIMCor. Of these, many are also publicly available for the community (see D7.8).

Virtual cohorts in SIMCor

In SIMCor, various virtual cohorts of humans and animals are generated. These include:

- TAVI – aortic valve cohorts, based on 97 geometries of patients with severe aortic stenosis being treated with TAVI.
 - Unfiltered 500 human aortic valve cohort
 - VC filtered on converging LVOT
 - VC filtered on diverging LVOT
 - VC filtered on angle below 20 degrees
 - VC filtered on angle between 20 and 40 degrees
 - VC filtered on angle above 40 degrees.
- PAPS – pulmonary artery cohort, based on 50 patient and 41 porcine data sets.
 - An unfiltered cohort of >4000 human pulmonary arteries
 - An unfiltered cohort of >2000 porcine pulmonary arteries
 - A virtual cohort matching the human baseline population of 50 patients
 - A virtual cohort matching the porcine baseline population of 41 animals
 - A virtual cohort matching the 10 animals of the chronic animal experiment

For details, refer to D7.8.

Application of virtual cohorts

Device effect simulation studies

Validated virtual cohorts of human or animal populations are extremely valuable to simulate realistic physiology and response, e.g., to predict the adverse effect of a device implantation. This is relevant for device development, testing or validation of medical devices in the context of in-vitro models, animal studies and human studies.

The virtual cohort can be used to evaluate efficacy, utility, and safety of the medical device of interest by performing an in-silico device implantation. The device effect simulations can be performed by using fast-to-evaluate reduced-order models, which provide first order approximations of the relevant factors that confound the implanted device. High-fidelity, more computationally-demanding models should be applied on high-performance computing infrastructures. Thus, the virtual cohorts are used to predict the implanted device effect, through reduced-order or high-order simulation results.

Device effect simulations in SIMCor

Virtual cohorts were employed to investigate deployment and post-implant effects as follows:

- Fast-to-evaluate model of TAVI implantation to evaluate *paravalvular leakage* (PVL) (see D8.7 – *Reduced order model (PHI, M30)*¹⁶)
- High-fidelity TAVI implantation to evaluate PVL and role of calcifications (D9.2 - *Device specific models (IIB, M24)*¹⁷)
- High-fidelity PAPS implantation and effect simulations for different engineering metrics, such as stresses, strains and hemodynamic parameters, as well as clinical endpoints such as device migration (see D9.2)
- Fast-to-evaluate model for the implantation of PAPS and subsequent hemodynamic assessment.

In-silico trials

An **in-silico trial** refers to the use of individualised computer simulations on a cohort of human or animal data, during the development or regulatory evaluation of a medicinal product, medical device, or medical intervention.

In-silico trials aim to reduce, refine or replace real clinical trials which need to be specified in advance. The planning of the in-silico trials should be compliant with the principles of simulation studies¹⁸. In the case of implantable medical devices, such simulation studies could refer to the use of virtual cohorts to investigate the deployment of devices or their adverse effect post-implantation, to determine the safety, efficacy and performance of the medical device under investigation. Such in-silico trials also help estimate the impact of in-silico methods and technologies on clinical and preclinical trial outcomes and for the assessment of broader effects on patient safety, animal welfare and industry workflow.

In-silico trial workflow

Analysis of in-silico trials on the outcome of device effects based on virtual cohorts need to be performed in a **secured statistical environment**. This can be realised through a dedicated in-silico trial workflow/framework that connects the virtual cohort generation and the device effect simulation outcomes with that of the trial design and the analysis environment. Such a representative in-silico trial workflow, illustrated in Figure 2, is detailed in *D10.1 – In-silico clinical trial impact assessment framework (ECRIN, M12)*¹⁹. The resulting process should allow storage and secure transfer of the information and/or data, between these building blocks of the in-silico trial workflow. This is considered as the bare minimum to give transparency and to allow repeatability of trial results.

Figure 2: Workflow for an in-silico trial.

¹⁶ This deliverable will become publicly available in Zenodo by June 2024.

¹⁷ This deliverable is confidential, thus not publicly available, but can be requested to Michael Stiehm (michael.stiehm@uni-rostock.de).

¹⁸ Burton et al., The design of simulation studies in medical statistics. *Stat Med.* 2006. 25: 4279

¹⁹ Aydin, B., & Ohmann, C. (2021). SIMCor. Deliverable 10.1: In-silico trial impact assessment framework (ECRIN, M12). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6353628>.

In-silico trial workflow – a SIMCor platform

The in-silico clinical trial design is specified within the analysis environment and then communicated to the VCG, which produces a trial-specific cohort. The data generated are transferred to the analysis environment, where the in-silico trial is run according to the defined design and the results are documented. This process is cyclic and repeated as often as required. If all necessary results have been achieved, the process is closed, and the results are explored, and a decision is taken. The workflow is summarised in Figure 2.

For details on the SIMCor VRE web interface and how to use the VRE in the context of virtual cohort generation and in-silico trial, we refer to *D3.5 - Web-based interface (UTBV, M36)*²⁰. A representative in-silico trial workflow is detailed in SIMCor D10.1.

VRE for generating and using virtual cohorts

To support critical and sensitive workflows such as the in-silico trial one, a platform or integrated infrastructure that enables the research community to not only store, process, share data, but also run simulations and analyse results, becomes indispensable. Across domains and scientific communities, there is an increasing number of such collaborative integrated infrastructures, often referred to as ‘*trusted research environment (TRE)*’, ‘*virtual research environment (VRE)*’, ‘*model execution environments (MEE)*’, etc. Description of such public infrastructures is beyond the scope of this SOP, and we refer to a few example environments^{21,22} and literature^{23,24}.

Within the context of virtual cohorts discussed in this document, a secured research platform in the form of VRE facilitates all the steps of an in-silico trial workflow. The entire workflow, starting from virtual cohort generation to device effect simulation, and final statistical analysis, is implemented in the VRE (see Figure 3). Using the tools provided by the web-based interface of VRE, the user can run a complete in-silico clinical trial pipeline.

²⁰ This deliverable is confidential and thus not publicly accessible, but can be requested to Lucian Itu (lucian.itu@unitbv.ro).

²¹ Berlin Institute of Health / Charité Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for sensitive data -

<https://www.bihealth.org/en/translation/network/digital-medicine/bihcharite-virtual-research-environment>.

²² <https://simcor.unitbv.ro/>

²³ Bubak M. et al., 2021. The EurValve model execution environment. *Interface Focus* 11, 2021- <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsfs.2020.0006>

²⁴ Kavianpour S, et al.,. Next-Generation Capabilities in Trusted Research Environments: Interview Study. *J Med Internet Res*. 2022 Sep 20;24(9). doi: 10.2196/33720.

Figure 3: Workflow of the SIMCor VRE: (a) the virtual cohorts are generated and stored in the VRE data repository. Subsequently, (b) the device effect simulations are conducted by virtually deploying the given implantable medical device within the virtual cohort of interests, using the fast-to-evaluate or high-fidelity deployment models. (c) The simulation results pertaining to the device effects, as determined by the high-fidelity (on external computers) and/or the fast-to-evaluate models are stored in a format that is specifically designed to communicate with (d) the R-Statistical Environment deployed on the VRE. This environment allows the user to perform statistical analyses on the simulation results.

The R-Statistical Environment of the VRE enables to perform clinical trials, data analysis and statistical computation on virtual cohort groups and device implantation simulation data.

The SIMCor platform - A VRE for in-silico trial workflow

The SIMCor platform is cloud-based VRE is designed to provide a set of tools for

1. virtual cohort generation and validation,
2. simulation of device implantation and evaluation of device performance,
3. in-silico trials.

The in-silico trial workflow embeds and connects with the corresponding toolboxes (VCG, simulation methods, statistical tools) as part of the single integrated VRE.

The virtual cohorts are generated and stored in the VRE Drive. Subsequently, the device effect simulations are conducted by virtually deploying the given implantable medical device within the virtual cohort of interests, using the fast-to-evaluate or high-fidelity deployment models. The simulation results pertaining to the device effects, as determined by the high-fidelity (on external computers) and/or the fast-to-evaluate models are stored in a format that is specifically designed to communicate with the statistical R-Statistical Environment deployed on the VRE. This environment allows the user to perform statistical analyses on the simulation results.

The specific statistical test needs to be selected by the user. In fact, the R-Statistical Environment is the analysis stage of the in-silico trial. Thereafter, the VRE automatically creates a report (in .pdf format) that includes information regarding the study cohort (i.e., demographics, features, etc.) and clearly visualised graphs, figures and/or tables of the statistical analyses.

For further details on SIMCor VRE web interface and how to use the VRE in the context of virtual cohort generation and in-silico trial, we refer to D3.5.

Outlook

This document focuses on providing guidance for the generation and validation of virtual cohorts to be used in in-silico clinical trials for evaluation of medical devices. The definition of a virtual cohort used in this document strongly links synthetic data elements, such as synthetic 3D geometries and boundary conditions, to physiology-based models, as only this combination facilitates to mimic physiology of real patient cohorts. Therefore, the **design of the virtual cohort is strongly linked to the context of use investigated** within the in-silico clinical trials.

Based on the chosen design, the emphasis on different aspects of this guidance document might differ from case to case. For example, if very large real-world data sets are used for generation of the virtual cohort, the patient-level validation step might already be the focus of the validation efforts, as it can be assumed that the real-world dataset sufficiently mimics the entire range of population characteristics.

While this document focuses on the generation and validation of virtual cohorts to be used in in-silico clinical trials, the methodology is widely applicable. Further examples for the **need of virtual cohorts** are to generate **standardised patient populations** for evaluation and comparison of numerical models, **de-identification of real-world data sets** via virtual cohorts mimicking them or creating large samples mimicking population characteristics for the **training of data-driven models**.

Despite the differences in context of use of the virtual cohort, strong emphasis should be placed on the validation. While virtual cohorts are ideal for sharing clinical data in a de-identified way, the use of virtual cohorts must always be considered with respect to the context of use for which they have been developed. This context of use will largely affect the parameters, models and data elements included in the cohort. Also, it might affect the population characteristics for which the cohort was validated. These aspects should be considered while utilising virtual cohorts from open sources and additional cross-validation steps might be necessary.

Applications

In the subsequent two sections, we will present the practical examples of how virtual cohorts are generated and readily considered for an in-silico trial in a VRE. To this end:

- **Part B** reports the application of virtual cohort of aortic valve geometries, to study the effect of TAVI device deployment, based on different types of aortic valve geometries (e.g., valves with converging or diverging LVOTs (D7.6)).
- **Part C** presents the VCG for the PAPS use case. This tool is not yet embedded in the VRE, but the strategy for its embedding and use is described.

Part B: application of TAVI VC and in-silico trial in the VRE

Introduction

Clinical need - aortic valve stenosis

Aortic valve stenosis is characterised by the inability of the aortic heart valve to completely open, creating a narrowing, which obstructs the blood flow into the aorta, and subsequently to the rest of the body. The *transcatheter aortic valve implantation* (TAVI) procedure is a minimally invasive treatment for patients with aortic valve stenosis, in which the native aortic valve is replaced using an artificial valve prosthesis. Despite TAVI being successfully employed over the past two decades, peri- and post-procedural complications are reported in the literature¹². Therefore, TAVI devices are subject to continuous development to improve current devices, extend their indications and to overcome the current complications.

Virtual cohorts help evaluate TAVI devices: in-silico models are often sought to simulate aortic valve dynamics, before and after treatment. The geometries generated by a virtual cohort generator offer a realistic representation of patient populations, for the development and optimisation of the TAVI device. Furthermore, they also allow for evaluating geometries that are underrepresented, or more interestingly steer us to investigate when the implanted device is likely to fail. Thus, directly benefiting the in-silico trials to study the safety, efficacy and procedural complications during and after a TAVI.

The following sections briefly sketch the entire workflow as addressed in SIMCor. Given the limited scope of this SOP document, the methodological details and results are rather brief and best referred to in the respective deliverable documents, as indicated.

Generation of unfiltered virtual cohorts of stenosed aortic valve

The virtual cohort generator for the TAVI use case is based on a baseline dataset of 97 stenotic peak-systolic aortic valve geometries. The relevant methodology of the pre-processing steps and the implementation details of the virtual cohort generator model are described in D7.1 - D7.5. Also, *D7.6 - Proof of principle of the complete virtual patient generator (TUE, M24)*²⁵ is of relevance. The corresponding methodology and resulting virtual cohort of aortic valve geometries are reported in Verstraeten et al.²⁶.

As described in D7.8, the model generates a user-defined number of synthetic aortic valve geometries, with the following data elements:

1. For each individual virtual patient, the aortic valve anatomy.
2. For each individual anatomy, eight geometric features as shown in Figure 4.

²⁵ This deliverable is confidential and thus not publicly accessible, but can be requested to Wouter Huberts (W.Huberts@tue.nl).

²⁶ Verstraeten S, Hoeijmakers M, Tonino P, Brüning J, Capelli C, van de Vosse F, Huberts W. Generation of synthetic aortic valve stenosis geometries for in silico trials. *Int J Numer Method Biomed Eng*. 2023 Nov 14:e3778. doi: 10.1002/cnm.3778

Figure 4: Schematic picture of the features extracted from the valve geometries. LVOT: left ventricular outflow tract; STJ: sino-tubular-junction; AVA: aortic valve area.

Principle of selection of virtual cohort - 'Filter'

Of the various geometric shape descriptors of the aortic valve, two anatomical features that affect the TAVI implantation are investigated further in Verstraeten et al.:

- a. The angle between *left ventricular outflow tract* (LVOT) and the ascending aorta (θ).
- b. LVOT shape being either converging or diverging.

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of an aortic valve geometry. The definition used to determine the angle between the ascending aorta and the LVOT (a) with a convergent (dashed) and divergent (dotted) LVOT (b)

These morphologies (see Figure 5) influence the occurrence of complications, such as conduction problems and *paravalvular leakage* (PVL). While conduction problems are a post-implantation anomaly that is likely to demand pacemaker dependency²⁷, PVL is a complication that can occur during a TAVI procedure²⁸.

PVL might be more common for patients with a larger angle between the LVOT and the ascending aorta, or for patients with a non-tubular LVOT (e.g., a converging or diverging LVOT). Therefore, users can request for specific cohorts that can be selected based on the angle between the LVOT and the

²⁷ Ishizu K, Murakami N, Morinaga T, et al. Impact of tapered-shape left ventricular outflow tract on pacemaker rate after transcatheter aortic valve replacement. *Heart Vessels*. 2022;37:1-11.

²⁸ Condado JF, Corrigan FE III, Lerakis S, et al. Anatomical risk models for paravalvular leak and landing zone complications for balloon expandable transcatheter aortic valve replacement. *Catheter Cardiovasc Interv*. 2017;90(4):690-700.

aorta or based on their shape (converging or diverging). Thus, these two geometric features, based on LVOT, become the criteria for clinically driven filtering of the synthetic geometries.

Figure 6: Schematic flowchart of how one synthetic geometry generated within the VCG, based on the user-defined filtering criteria - LVOT angle or LVOT shape (convergent/divergent).

Thus, as described in Figure 6, the cycle is repeated for a number of virtual patients that satisfy the user-requested filtering criteria. The resulting aortic valve geometries and their corresponding surface measurements are saved in the VRE Drive (see Figure 3) for the next step of device effect simulation.

Fast-to-evaluate deployment model for TAVI implantation

The device-effect simulation starts from the virtual model of TAVI implant and the virtual geometry of a stenosed aortic valve as inputs and performs the virtual treatment using an effect simulation. The virtual treatment to determine the alignment of the TAVI device during implantation is evaluated. Based on the outcome of the effect simulation, the virtual cohorts can be categorised as binary, either a positive or negative, in terms of an adverse effect (e.g., PVL).

Practically, once a new population of virtual cohorts using the LVOT filters is generated and stored in the VRE, they become input to evaluate the effect of device deployment or post-implantation effects. This step can be accomplished using a fast-to-evaluate simulation or a high-fidelity time-consuming offline process. As outlined in Part A of this SOP, fast-to-evaluate surrogate models become indispensable not only for validation schemes, but also for practical efficiency during in-silico trials. In the case of TAVI device effect simulation, the fast-to-evaluate model performs a near real-time simulation to attain insights on treatment effects for the virtual cohort of interest. This is carried out with the fast-to-evaluate model, which is set up in such a way that it can be trained by high-fidelity simulations and measurements. For details on the fast-to-evaluate methodology, refer to *D8.8 - Fast-to-evaluate TAVI model based on multi-patch NURBS (TUE, M28)*²⁹.

Herewith, a brief description on how the virtual cohort and device effect simulations impact in-silico trials is presented for completeness. In device effect simulation, the TAVI implantation procedure is mimicked by a cylindrical stent, which expands around a guidewire. As shown in Figure 7, the guidewire model translates/rotates as it advances in aortic geometry and comes in contact with the leaflets at specific timesteps. At any given timestep, a computed solution from the device-effect simulation can be used to estimate the paravalvular leakage area. Thus, a device-effect simulation model provides insight into the positioning of the stent and, through post-processing operations, quantifies the areas subject to PVL.

²⁹ This deliverable will be made public in Zenodo by June 2024.

Figure 7: Visualising the device-effect simulation (aortic wall, leaflets, cylinder, forces) at different time steps. The artery wall is shown in red; the guidewire is shown in blue, and the device is shown in beige. The time steps (a) $t=0.01s$, (b) $t=0.04s$, (c) $t=0.075s$ (d) The catheter at the end of expansion (beige) and contact forces acting on the device (green) are shown for a convergent synthetic geometry.

The resulting contact forces from the simulation study as well as other engineering metrics are readily stored in the VRE. Thus, made available for in-silico trials as input to predict patient-specific treatment outcomes like calcifications or leakage, alongside the statistical environment in the VRE.

Summary: in-silico trial workflow for virtual cohorts in the VRE

This subsection summarises the key steps of the process, from virtual cohort generation to performance assessment, in the context of the in-silico clinical trial workflow implemented in VRE. The steps for running a complete TAVI in-silico trial pipeline³⁰ in a VRE (illustrated in Figure 3), are:

1. Register a new user account in the VRE - <https://simcor.unitbv.ro/apps/registration/>.
2. Create a new working directory in the VRE Drive. This directory is used to acquire input data and store output data.
3. Generate a new population of virtual cohorts using the TAVI virtual cohort generation models available in the VRE, representing realistic anatomical models of stenosed aortic valves corresponding to the systolic phase.
4. Apply NURBS (*Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines*) templates to the virtual cohorts generated at step 3. This is a manual step that currently needs to be executed outside the VRE. Note that the STL-files generated can also be exported to use them for simulations using in-house or commercial finite/volume elements software.
5. Simulate the TAVI device implantation using a fast-to-evaluate model. The model details are described in *D8.8*.
6. Run clinical trials and conduct research activities in the R-Statistical Environment. Details of the environment are given in *D10.1*.

For details on the SIMCor VRE web interface and the entire manual on how to use the VRE in the context of virtual cohort generation and in-silico trial, we refer you to D3.5.

³⁰ SIMCor deliverable - D3.5: Web-based interface (UTBV, M36). Document providing details on the user interface and user profiles of the Virtual Research Environment (VRE). Please note, this document is restricted to consortium.

Part C: application of PAPS VC in the VRE

Note: The validated virtual cohorts and virtual cohort generators for the PAPS use case are not yet implemented into the VRE. However, the methodology used to generate the virtual cohorts, and for selection based on user-defined sub-cohorts, is finalised and will be described subsequently. This section will be updated once the methodology is implemented into the VRE.

Introduction

Clinical need – heart failure

Pulmonary artery pressure sensors are used to infer cardiac filling pressures in *heart failure* (HF) patients to facilitate their medical management. PAPS are implantable devices which are deployed into the pulmonary artery of the patient, by means of a minimally invasive catheter procedure. It is necessary that the implanted PAPS device does not cause adverse events like migration, vessel perforation or rupture, inflammation or thrombosis.

The main feature of interest provided by the virtual cohorts for the PAPS use-case is the 3D geometry of the pulmonary artery, as this anatomy is used for subsequent simulation of device implantation and device effect simulations. These anatomies are further characterised by anatomical measures that are of interest for the device implantation, such as vessel diameters and lengths.

Virtual cohort of PAPS geometries

Even though the generation of the virtual cohorts for PAPS is also based on statistical shape models, a different approach was chosen compared to the TAVI use case. While in the TAVI use case, geometries are generated directly by the VCG and can be accepted or discarded based on different filtering strategies, 2 large virtual cohorts were generated for the PAPS use case, 1 for porcine and 1 for human pulmonary arteries (see D7.8). These virtual cohorts mimic the underlying real data as closely as possible. As for subsequent analysis cohorts with specific parameter distributions or characteristics might be necessary, a filtering procedure was then developed to identify matching geometries from this large sample. Using this approach, specific porcine or human cohorts fulfilling user-specified requirements can be generated, while ensuring that they are a subset of a validated cohort.

Despite the different approach in generation of the filtered cohorts, the PAPS VCG still adheres to all steps described in Part A of this document. Currently, the patient-specific and self-validation steps of the tiered validation approach are finalised (see D7.8), whereas cross-validation is work in progress.

Generation of unfiltered virtual cohorts for pigs and humans

The 2 validated, baseline cohorts for porcine and human pulmonary arteries are described in detail in D7.8. Therefore, the key aspects of these cohorts are described here, that are necessary to understand the implementation of the VCG at the VRE.

The virtual cohorts for the porcine and human virtual cohorts follow slightly different design strategies. The reason for that is, that the heterogeneity of the side-branch configuration observed in humans was significantly higher than that in pigs. While most of the animals had the same number of side branches originating from the left and right pulmonary artery, this number of side branches varied strongly in the human pulmonary artery. As statistical shape models require common topology for their proper definition, this required adaptation of the method used for generation of synthetic porcine pulmonary arteries for the human use case.

Porcine pulmonary artery

The common topology of the pulmonary artery observed in pigs allowed using a well-established method for centreline based statistical shape models. Here, the vascular tree is parameterised using a centreline with an equal number of vertices per line segment. For each vertex, the diameter of the

vessel is also encoded in this data structure. Thus, a principal component analysis could be implemented to describe the shape variance observed in the porcine data set.

Human pulmonary artery

Due to the observed heterogeneity in side-branch configuration, the above-mentioned approach could not be utilised and was adapted. The generation of synthetic human pulmonary arteries was separated into 2 steps:

1. First, centreline-based representations of the main, left, and right pulmonary artery were generated. From this information a statistical shape model of the main bifurcation was generated, which allowed subsequent generation of synthetic geometries.
2. These synthetic geometries were then extended by branching vessels based on the distributions and characteristics observed in the real data set. This included the number of side branches, their position, orientation, and diameter.

This approach allowed to generate pulmonary artery surface geometries with the same main, left, and right pulmonary artery but different branching vessel configurations.

It is important to note, that no sex- or age-dependent differences in any anatomical properties was observed in the human pulmonary arteries. This finding was initially not expected, as in the healthy aorta, for example, age-dependent growth is well documented, and the average diameters of men is larger than that of women. However, these findings could not be replicated in our real cohort of pulmonary artery geometries. Therefore, neither age nor sex were included as parameters in the virtual cohort. Of course, to perform these simulations, also information on further boundary conditions, such as the volume flow waveform ejected from the right ventricular outflow tract into the pulmonary artery is of importance. However, due to the lack of sex- or age-dependent correlations with any anatomical properties, generation of anatomical boundary conditions and hemodynamic boundary conditions can be performed independently from one another.

Planned implementation in the VRE

The entire validated virtual cohorts of the porcine and human pulmonary artery are made available via the VRE, including the individual surface geometries, centrelines, as well as a table containing all anatomical properties. Simultaneously, patient- and animal specific anatomies are provided.

Principle for selection of virtual cohorts

While the large virtual cohort provides all relevant information for device implantation and device effect simulation, it is lacking usability with respect to filtering. User-specific requirements for different sub-cohorts can vary strongly. For example, users might be interested in specifically narrow or wide pulmonary arteries to assess whether risks for device migration or vessel perforation are increasing. Furthermore, a selection methodology was necessary to identify geometries matching a real geometry as closely as possible. This feature is required, among others, to assess the patient-specific and the self-validation aspect of the SIMCor validation strategy of virtual cohorts. Also, a virtual cohort representation of the chronic animal trial conducted in frames of the project had to be generated using this approach.

To facilitate these cohorts based on user requirements or aiming to match real cohorts, 2 methods (i.e., L1-norm, procrustes analysis) have been implemented. Through these methods, 3 sub-cohorts matching real cohorts have been generated so far:

1. A virtual representation of the 10 pigs of the chronic animal experiment conducted in SIMCor.
2. A virtual representation of the pigs on which the statistical shape model of the porcine pulmonary artery was trained.
3. A virtual representation of the patients on which the statistical shape model of the human pulmonary artery was trained.

Selection method II - L1-norm

The selection method is based on calculating the relative L1-Norm [%] for selected geometric parameters between the real shape to be matched and all synthetic cases. The user can specify requirements or parameters of importance by setting maximum and minimum deviations that are accepted individually for each geometric parameter by a user (see Figure 8). Furthermore, the user can specify a value of 100%, which results in the parameter to be neglected during the matching procedure. For example, to identify matched porcine cohorts, 7 geometric parameters were used: diameters and lengths of the major vessel segments, main, left, and right pulmonary artery, and the bifurcation angle between left and right pulmonary artery.

Animal_ID	L_MPA	D_MPA	L_RPA	D_RPA	L_LPA	D_LPA	Angle
SIMCor_C1		64.1300	18.0100	101.8400	9.5600	81.6300	10.1900

Margin [+-%]	100	25	25	25	25	25	25
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Figure 8: GUI allowing to set individually margins for each geometric parameter describing the pulmonary artery shape.

Planned implementation in the VRE

- The GUI for specifying the importance of the different parameters will be implemented directly into the VRE.
- Users can specify whether they would like to match an existing cohort and have to upload a CSV file containing the parameters of the cohort samples, or they can specify a range for each parameter to select geometries from. Both approaches can result in too restrictive search requirements which can provide no matching results. In this case users are informed.
- Users can specify how many matching geometries they want per real case, if a matching cohort is generated, or for their overall sample, in case a filtered cohort is generated.

Figure 9 shows 3 selected synthetic porcine pulmonary artery geometries that match a given real geometry (left) pig pulmonary artery (right, synthetic cohort) with the minimal L1-Norm.

Figure 9: Example of three selected synthetic cases from the overall database, matching a real porcine pulmonary artery (left).

Once the selection procedure is finished, a CSV file describing the synthetic cohort and including information about selected synthetic case names, the real case that is matched, all geometric parameters of these cases, and the L1-Norm is exported. Using this information, distribution

information of the sub-cohort generated using this procedure can be compared against the distribution of the full unfiltered virtual cohort, as well as the criteria specified for the selection procedure. Furthermore, for the human cohort we added the possibility of the sub-cohort selection based on demographic parameters such as select all males or all females as well as cases belonging to the defined age range can be selected.

Selection method II - Procrustes analysis

An alternative selection method using Procrustes analysis was also implemented. This selection procedure requires 3D shape information encoded in a centreline representation of the pulmonary artery, which also contains information of the diameter of the vessel. Therefore, this approach is only suitable to generate sub-cohorts matching specific cohorts of which the 3D-anatomies are known. An exemplary use case could be the generation of a large synthetic cohort of porcine pulmonary arteries matching the 10 chronic animals investigated in SIMCor. The method is based on the calculation of the Procrustes distance, which is computed using the sum of squared differences between the corresponding points in the target shape X and the transformed shape Z, which is then normalised by the scale S of the target shape X. The scale of X is calculated as:

$$S = \sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_{i=1}^N (X_{i,j} - \text{mean}(X_j))^2$$

which is the sum of squared elements of a centred version of X where the columns of X have mean 0. The Procrustes distance D is thus computed as:

$$D = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_{i=1}^N (X_{i,j} - Z_{i,j})^2}{S}$$

ranging from 0 (perfect match) to 1 if the comparison shape Y is scaled. If the comparison shape is not scaled, the value can be above 1.

The different selection methods result in different matched virtual cohorts as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Comparison of the 10 pulmonary artery geometries of 10 real pigs (chronic animal cohort) and the synthetic cohorts matched based on the Procrustes analysis (middle row), and the L1-norm (bottom row).

Fast-to-evaluate deployment model for PAPS

A fast deployment model for assessing the hemodynamic effects of the PAPS after implantation was developed. This model utilises the surface geometry and centreline information to automatically position the PAPS device and calculate a wall-bound position after implantation. The user can specify:

- The valid diameter range of the implantation site,
- Whether the implantation should be performed in the left or right pulmonary artery, or whether there is no preference,
- The number of implantations performed per virtual patient.

This model aims to mimic the real implantation procedure, where the rotation of the device around the centreline is not controlled, and the implantation site is only selected via the target diameter. Using this approach, large numbers of pulmonary artery geometries with implanted PAPS devices for subsequent hemodynamic analysis can be generated. However, the hemodynamic analysis must be performed outside of the VRE and only the results can then be uploaded as a CSV file for subsequent in-silico analysis.

Contingencies

If the researcher cannot adhere to the content of these SOP instructions for justified reasons, then deviation from the procedure must be documented and appropriate actions must be taken, considering SOP revision if relevant.

Attachments

None.

Publication policy

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When using the current SOP, please acknowledge SIMCor as follows: *Huberts, W. et al. (2023). SIMCor. Deliverable 4.3: SOP on virtual cohort generation and validation (TUE, M36).*